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MED-GOLD

Turning climate-related information into added value for traditional **MED**iterranean **G**rape, **O**Live and **D**urum wheat food systems

Deliverable 4.2

Design of innovative agro-climatic systems for durum wheat

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Brief Description	This report presents the ideas and concepts collected among project partners, agronomists and farmers in order to build up a climate service prototype for durum wheat. Each component of this new agro-climatic information and decision support system is described. Preliminary results are presented as well. This report presents, often in a graphical and intuitive manner, the sequence of stages needed to set up an operational climate service in the Mediterranean area applicable over a wide range of temporal scales and with the possibility of being implemented in other areas of the World that are (or will be) suitable for durum wheat cultivation.	
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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This deliverable describes the design of the MED-GOLD prototype climate service for durum wheat.

More specifically, it provides:

- the identification of the different components of the new climate service, from the raw data download to the application of crop impact models and risk assessment indicators tailored for durum wheat and calibrated on the three target locations identified in MED-GOLD for durum wheat in Italy (Ravenna, Foggia, Jesi). The procedure is designed to be extended to the wider Mediterranean area and eventually at the global level.
- The identification of the time scales of the climate service development and provision. These are split in two main branches: 1) the past climate and the near future, which are taken into account for both the development steps and the operational climate service provisioning, and 2) the further future climate at the decadal and multidecadal time scales, which are involved in the climate service provisioning only. Notably, the application of most of the MED-GOLD model to seasonal forecast data is almost ready to be implemented operationally (see RD.2). Furthermore, the several envisaged end-users of this new climate service are already trained to interpret the information resulting from such implementation (RD.1).
- A brief summary of the development phase, which is conducted in close collaboration with end-users (farmers and agronomists). This part, together with preliminary ensemble of seasonal forecasts implementations, has been extensively described by the first and second reports on the user feedback (RD.1 and RD.2) and is often mentioned in this document as well as it is an essential part of the innovative design characterized the main development steps of all the climate service component delivered by MED-GOLD.
- The final design of the main MED-GOLD components, which are mainly split in the description of the MED-GOLD ICT platform and of the procedures collecting and distributing the calibration and driving data to the impact models, and the impact models themselves, which are Delphi, Granoduro.net®, Clisagri and Wofost-ECroPS. These models are applied not only to the future climate, but also on the past climate. This is not only useful for calibration and validation, but also as a climate service *per se* according to the best year – worst year narrative of MED-GOLD (see RD.2), aiming at merging climatic statistical analyses and field experience in order to blend the added value from both sides.
- The discussion of the envisaged application of the MED-GOLD models at the global scale and at the decadal and multidecadal time-scale, with some preliminary results.
- The evaluation of the effects of climate change of durum wheat suitability. This analysis is quite new and definitely innovative compared to the standard climates service information based on the chain of climate and impact models. It aims at identifying new areas potentially prone to durum wheat cultivation, as well as areas losing this capacity in the future climate, because of global warming. The potential outcomes of this analysis clearly bears interesting application for climate adaptation and to drive sustainable investment in the future agriculture.
- The summary and conclusions.

With this deliverable, the project has contributed to the achievement of the following objectives (DOA, PartB Table1.1):

No.	Objective	Yes
1	To co-design, co-develop, test, and assess the added value of proof-of-concept climate services for olive, grape, and durum wheat	YES
2	To refine, validate, and upscale the three pilot services with the wider European and global user communities for olive, grape, and durum wheat	YES
3	To ensure replicability of MED-GOLD climate services in other crops/climates (e.g., coffee) and to establish links to policy making globally	YES
4	To implement a comprehensive communication and commercialization plan for MED-GOLD climate services to enhance market uptake	NO
5	To build better informed and connected end-user communities for the global olive oil, wine, and pasta food systems and related policy making	NO

1. INTRODUCTION

1.1. PURPOSE

Climate change is already affecting agricultural production through changes in the mean climate variables and in the frequency and amplitude of climate extremes [RD.3, RD.4, RD.5]. These negative trends will further accelerate in the future climate, posing an increasingly larger pressure on the agricultural systems. The climate related risk is particularly high for the Mediterranean area, which is one of the hottest spots of global warming. Notably, durum wheat cultivation is already unsuitable in the Middle East, where it was originated.

MED-GOLD is raising awareness on these issues, but also collecting the concerns and the experience of farmers and agronomists on the risk related to climate change. With the knowledge of the past and current climate, and considering the plausible future scenarios, MED-GOLD is answering to the need of an efficient risk management for durum wheat cultivation in the Mediterranean area by setting up a tailored and efficient climate service prototype in order to foster climate change adaptation. Moreover, MED-GOLD will identify new opportunities that could be brought by the changing climate.

This deliverable describes the main modelling approaches composing the MED-GOLD climate service prototype for durum wheat, namely: Delphi, a crop model developed and maintained by the CNR; a decision supporting system developed and maintained Granoduro.net® by HORTA; Clisagri and Wofost-ECroPS, which are respectively a risk assessment software and a crop model developed by the JRC.

The design of the MED-GOLD climate service prototype for durum wheat has involved a tight interaction with end-users, including BARILLA. All the development steps are conceptually an integral component of the prototyping design. The development and co-designing phase is a result of two users' feedback steps (which are reported in RD.1 and RD.2) that were focused on the understanding of recent past climate and the exploitation of the recent development and availability of seasonal forecasts.

The previous users' feedback reports (RD.1 and RD.2) confirmed a first broad success of the level of development of these tools by end-users, which had seen their general expectations being met (even though the workshop that was supposed to be organized in order to provide some of the material for the second report has been postponed because of the covid-19 pandemic). As a result, the current development stage successfully brings the probabilistic information (required when considering seasonal forecasts) together with the understanding of its value to end-users (RD.1). However, considering all ensemble members of the seasonal forecasts (e.g., as included in Copernicus-CDS) could be challenging (RD.2) for the IT infrastructure of the end-users adopting the MED-GOLD impact models. For this reason, and in order to ensure the replicability aspect of the project, this document describes in detail the preparation phase of the data to run the MED-GOLD models on the seasonal forecast data downloaded from the Copernicus-CDS structure (already semi-operational). This task is performed by ENEA and BeeToBit.

This document also describes how the MED-GOLD climate service design may be applied with innovative climate information provided by decadal predictions as well as to the classical climate change scenario simulations. In the latter case, alternative approaches could be deployed in addition to the already developed MED-GOLD models assessing the future feasibility of durum wheat agriculture at the global scale.

This report ultimately defines the shape and the last steps needed to finalise the MED-GOLD climate service prototype.

1.2. SCOPE

This document describes the different observational and modelling components involved in the design of the MED-GOLD climate service prototype for durum wheat. Figure 1-1 depicts the main components of the MED-GOLD climate service and a description of the development strategy carried out within MED-GOLD.

Figure 1-1: Schematics of the MED-GOLD design of innovative climate services for durum wheat. The coloured arrow (top of the plot) represents the time scales of the climate data involved in the development of the MED-GOLD climate service components: green for recent past, yellow for seasonal forecasts, orange for decadal predictions and red for climate scenarios. The current development stage involves mainly the recent past and the seasonal forecasts. It accounts for a data processing phase and the implementation of the new modelling approaches developed within MED-GOLD through two confrontation steps with farmers, agronomists and professionals involved with different stages of the durum wheat farm to fork production and processing chain. The MED-GOLD development steps are conducted through model implementation and data analysis of the past and near future climate. The results of such development will be extended to the further future time scales, and to the global scale.

With reference to Figure 1-1, data for the recent past include agronomic data, climate observations and hindcasts (i.e. seasonal forecasts generated for the past) are discussed in Section 3.1.1 of this document. The processing steps, to make this data usable by the MED-GOLD impact models, are described in Section 3.1.2. The MED-GOLD proposed modeling approaches are described in Section 3.2. Notably, most of them are already implemented on past climate data and can potentially be run operationally using seasonal forecasts data.

Extending the use of the MED-GOLD modelling approaches is relatively straightforward as the format of climate data is fully consistent with that of the seasonal forecast. However, this step requires separating the concept of decadal predictions from the one of climate projections, which is often source of confusion even among scientists. This distinction is of capital importance for a clear and effective climate service provisioning for durum wheat and for agricultural applications in general. A detailed discussion on this important point is in Section 4.1.1. The data processing for the climate scenarios is described in Section 4.1.2. The envisaged implementation of the MED-GOLD modelling approaches on decadal predictions and climate scenarios is discussed in Section 4.2.1. Finally, Section 4.2.2 describes a complementary approach (with respect to the ones already developed) that can be extremely useful when dealing with future time scales. This consists of the estimation of the effects of climate change on durum wheat suitability and the regional and global levels, which could allow identifying new areas where durum wheat can be profitably planted in the future.

1.3. DEFINITIONS AND ACRONYMS

1.3.1. DEFINITIONS

Concepts and terms used in this document and needing a definition are included in the following table:

Table 1-1 Definitions

Concept / Term	Definition
Delphi	A crop model developed and maintained by the JRC, providing durum wheat yield forecasts and scenarios to BARILLA
Granoduro.net®	A DSS developed and maintained by HORTA, used by most of the durum wheat provides and producers of BARILLA.
Clisagri	An R-software for climate related risk assessment developed by the JRC
Wofost-ECcroPS	The crop model developed by the JRC
R	R CRAN Software Foundation for statistical analyses
PYTHON	A popular and powerful scripting language
NetCDF	A portable and self-describing Common Data Format
GRIB	The data format of ECMWF

1.3.2. ACRONYMS

Acronyms used in this document and needing a definition are included in the following table:

Table 1-2 Acronyms

Acronym	Definition
ECMWF	European Center for Medium Range Weather Forecast
SEAS5	ECMWF Seasonal Forecasting System 5
CDS	The Copernicus Climate Data Store
SPEI	Standardized Precipitation Evapo-transpiration Index
EO	Earth Observations
NDVI	Normalized Differential Vegetation Index
DSS	Decision Support System
CDO	Climate Data Operator
RCP	Representative Concentration Pathways
CORDEX	Coordinated Regional climate model Experiment (similar to CMIP, but for regional scales)
CMIP	Coupled Model Intercomparison Project (the one promoted by the IPCC)
IPCC	Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change
FACE	Free-air concentration enrichment
MCYFS	JRC crop monitoring and forecasting system
ICT	Information and Communication Technology

2. REFERENCES

2.1. REFERENCE DOCUMENTS

The following documents, although not part of this document, amplify or clarify its contents. Reference documents are those not applicable and referenced within this document. They are referenced in this document in the form [RD.x]:

Table 2-1 Reference Documents

Ref.	Title	Code	Version	Date
[RD.1]	First Feedback report from users on durum wheat pilot service development	D 4.6	final	31/05/2019
[RD.2]	Second Feedback report from users on durum wheat pilot service development	D 4.7	final	30/04/2020
[RD.3]	Wheat yield loss attributable to heat waves, drought and water excess at the global, national and subnational scales	Zampieri et al.	final	2017
[RD.4]	Concurrent climate extremes in the key wheat producing regions of the world	Toreti et al.	final	2019
[RD.5]	RAgroClim: An R package for agro-climate services	Ceglar et al.	2	submitted
[RD.6]	Improving WOFOST model to simulate winter wheat phenology in Europe: Evaluation and effects on yield	Ceglar et al.	final	2019
[RD.7]	Durum wheat quality prediction in Mediterranean environments: From local to regional scale	Toscano et al.	final	2014
[RD.8]	Durum wheat modeling: The Delphi system, 11 years of observations in Italy..	Toscano et al.	final	2012
[RD.9]	A model of the growth and development of wheat incorporating responses to water and nitrogen	Porter et al.	final	1993
[RD.10]	A Precision Agriculture Approach for Durum Wheat Yield Assessment Using Remote Sensing Data and Yield Mapping.	Toscano et al.	final	2019
[RD.11]	Overview of near-term decadal Climate prediction and its Applications	González-Reviriego et al. BSC report	final	2018
[RD.12]	Atlantic influence on spring snowfall over the Alps in the past 150 years	Zampieri et al. ERL	final	2013
[RD.13]	Atlantic multi-decadal oscillation influence on weather regimes over Europe and the Mediterranean in spring and summer	Zampieri et al. Global Planetary Change	final	2016
[RD.14]	Impacts of the Atlantic Multidecadal Variability on North American summer climate and heat waves	Ruprich-Robert et al. JCLim	final	2018
[RD.15]	Multi-year prediction of European summer drought conditions for the agricultural sector	Solaraju-Murali et al. ERL	final	2019
[RD.16]	A web-based decision support system for managing durum wheat crops	Rossi et al. Advances in Decision Support Systems	final	2010
[RD.17]	Granoduro.net TM : a web-based decision support system to improve durum wheat sustainability.	Ruggeri et al. MPU Workshop. Bari	final	2012
[RD.18]	A multicomponent decision support system to manage Fusarium head blight and mycotoxins in durum wheat	Rossi, Manstretta et al. World Mycotoxin Journal	final	2015
[RD.19]	A simulation model for the development of brown rust epidemics in winter wheat	Rossi et al., European Journal of Plant Pathology	final	1997
[RD.20]	Understanding and reproducing regional diversity of climate impacts on wheat yields: current approaches, challenges and data driven limitation	Zampieri et al. ERL	final	2018
[RD.21]	The climate of the zone of origin of Mediterranean durum wheat (<i>Triticum durum</i> Desf.) landraces affects their agronomic performance	Royo et al. Genetic Resources and Crop Evolution	final	2014
[RD.22]	Climate resilience of the top ten wheat producers in the Mediterranean and the Middle East	Zampieri et al. Regional Environmental Change	final	2020

3. DOCUMENT CONTENT

This chapter describes current state of the MED-GOLD climate service prototype aiming at interpreting the recent-past variability and to be applied to seasonal forecasts, developed as a result of the 2-steps interaction with end-users (see [RD.1-RD.2]). Past and near future data are described in Section 3.1, including agronomic and climate data description (Section 3.1.1), the pre-processing steps to be performed before using the climate information (Sections 3.1.2-3.1.3.) as well as the interface provided to actually reach and use such data (Section 3.1.4, ANNEX A). The MED-GOLD modelling approaches are described and discussed in Section 3.2.

3.1. PAST AND NEAR FUTURE DATA

3.1.1. AGRONOMIC AND CLIMATE DATA

The different time scales accounted in MED-GOLD are associated with different levels of decision making. Short-term weather forecasts can be used to plan field operations, such as field preparation for sowing, ploughing, fertilization, slurry and harvesting. Seasonal forecasts, from one month to one year ahead, can provide strategic information for farmers, such as variety selection and fertilization requirements. All this information is valuable only if interpreted through a solid agronomic knowledge and a robust knowledge of the past climate variability. For this reason, MED-GOLDS employs observational datasets for the past climatology as well as weather forecasts exercises conducted for the past i.e. the so-called hindcasts.

Seasonal predictions for mean, maximum, and minimum temperatures and total precipitation at both daily and monthly scales are obtained from the ECMWF System-5 (SEAS5) through the Copernicus-CDS. SEAS5 is the fifth generation of ECMWF’s seasonal forecasting system. It replaces the former ECMWF System 4 (S4) and uses the Integrated Forecast System, IFS, Cycle 43r1. The SEAS5 data available through the Copernicus CDS cover the period from 1993 to present, with two different streams of data: from 1993 to 2016 the model is run in hindcast mode (a forecast made for a period in the past using only information available before the beginning of the forecast) to produce 25 members for each run; after 2016, the model is run in a real forecast configuration to produce 51 members for each run. Compared to the S4 it includes a number of enhancements in the atmospheric resolution, land-surface initialisation and in the ocean model.

In the atmospheric component, the horizontal resolution has been increased from 80km to 36km with 91 vertical levels (the same as S4). Regarding the land-surface initialisation, the SEAS5 includes a new offline recalculation at the native atmospheric resolution with a revised precipitation forcing. Although this initialisation is still not perfect (the reanalysis and real-time assimilation are not the same), the tests performed show a good degree of consistency between the initialisation of SEAS5 re-forecast and real-time predictions. SEAS5 uses the new version of ocean model NEMO (Nucleus for European Modelling of the Ocean), with an upgraded model version, ocean physics and resolution. More specifically the resolution has been increased from 1 degree and 42 layers in S4 to 0.25 degrees and 75 layers in SEAS5. The ocean and sea-ice initial conditions are provided by the new ocean analysis and reanalysis ensemble (ORAS5).

Climate and agronomic data retrieved from satellite can be incorporated in the MED-GOLD climate service platform as well. In fact, the EO imagery can be analyzed using some of the currently operational Earth Observation system (MODIS9, Landsat8, Sentinel2 L2a and L1C). Indeed, a total of 3456 MODIS (2000-2018) to WP4 has already been processed and uploaded to MED-GOLD ICT platform.

Figure 3-1: Proposed methodology to include EO data in MED-GOLD.

The design for integrating satellite data in the MED-GOLD set of climate and agronomic data is represented in Figure 3-1. The first part of this integration implied the development of python scripts using APIs to download the data. Then, another set of scripts were developed to calculate the indexes based on time series considering the spectral availability according to each sensor. This phase implements free Python libraries such as `geopandas`, `gdal`, `shapely`, and `pandas`. This procedure allows deriving useful vegetation indexes such as NDVI, but also temperature and drought indexes that can be computed from the multispectral imagery and compared with standard observations and model results. Therefore, this data can be integrated and compared with the other climate and agronomical data already implemented and available in MED-GOLD over durum wheat areas in Italy and on other suitable areas in the world (see discussion in section 4.3).

Satellite data can be potentially useful also to estimate the current status of the crop during the growing season under examination. However, depending on the mission and the approach of the projects, acquisition in near real time is limited due to the post-processing time and the acquisition rate. The acquisition frequency to MODIS9 imagery is 8 days, Sentinel2 5 days and Landsat8 16 days. Furthermore, it takes between 1 or 3 weeks to be published. Moreover, the passive sensors can be affected by external factors as cloud cover. Another limitation is the spatial resolution of some sensors. As for agricultural applications, a continuous crop monitoring is possible with the support of platforms such as Sentinel 2 and Landsat8 taking into account both spatial and spectral resolutions. MODIS9 may be more suitable for large areas analysis.

3.1.2. CLIMATE DATA PROCESSING

The data processing workflow has four components:

- the data retrieval and storage;
- the data pre-processing, which prepares the raw data for the required computation
- a computation layer which includes the bias correction of seasonal forecast data and the computation of bioclimatic indicators;
- a data export layer where data are made available to the users or to other components of the MED-GOLD ICT Platform.

The MED-GOLD data processing system, whose design is described in Figure 3-2, builds on three free and open-source software packages, which provide the optimal functionality in different aspects of the processing chain:

- PYTHON scripts for data retrieval and updates from the Copernicus CDS.
- CDO functions to formatting data and to perform simple computations (e.g. derived variables such as wind speed or relative humidity, subdomain selection, regional statistics).
- R packages for more complex computations, such as bias correction and derivation of bioclimatic indicators.
- The workflow reported in Figure 3-2 shows also a possible structure of the file system which is generated for data processing. The rules applied to the structure of the folders and file names aim at enabling the use of the function `CST_Load`, to be used for the bias correction and to import seasonal forecast (needed to derive bioclimatic indices).

A preliminary implementation of the workflow described in Figure 3-2 and in the reminder of this section is available through the MED-GOLD repository (<https://start.med-gold.eu/source/durum/>)

Figure 3-2: MED-GOLD seasonal forecast data processing workflow.

DATA Retrieval

The backbone of the data retrieval process is the Copernicus CDS data interface. Seasonal forecasts, available in the Copernicus CDS, are released each month with initial conditions set at the first day of the month they are associated with. Usually, seasonal forecasts are made available the 15th day of the month while reanalysis are available in near real time with a delay of about two days. Therefore, reanalysis data (ERA5 and ERA5Land) are checked regularly on a daily basis whereas seasonal forecasts are checked every month and the rest of the data processing chain is activated when new seasonal forecast data are retrieved.

The data retrieval process follows also a slightly different path, owing to the different structures of the observational and climate prediction datasets.

Reanalysis data are organized in yearly files containing hourly data.

Seasonal forecast data contain daily data covering the entire time period of the forecast. Accumulated quantities, such as rainfall and solar radiation, are derived from the beginning of the forecast period. The scripts `MEDGOLD_UPDATE-SEASONAL_cdsapi.py` and `MEDGOLD_UPDATE-<OBSNAME>_cdsapi.py` are designed to check the existence of the datasets.

Pre-Processing

The processing of seasonal forecasts and reanalysis has two objectives: to prepare bias corrected data that are required by the other external applications (e.g., Granoduro.net® and Delphi) and to compute bio-climatic indicators that can be visualized on the MED-GOLD dashboard.

A key resource for the processing of climate data is the R package CStools (<https://cran.r-project.org/web/packages/CStools/index.html>) which provides all the required functionalities to a) find the data in the local file system; b) import data into the current workspace as standardized multi-dimensional arrays; c) perform the bias-correction as described in section 3.1.3 d) perform the skill assessment of the forecasts and d) prepare the output files in NetCDF format.

Therefore, the first operation performed on the raw climate data retrieved from the Copernicus Data Store is to format them in a way that is compatible with the standards adopted by CStools. Moreover, the bias-correction algorithm requires that both the climate forecast and the reference observational data are aligned w.r.t. their temporal resolution.

Finally, as the other components need climate parameters which are not directly available (e.g. wind speed and relative humidity), additional calculations must be performed.

The data formatting handled with two shell scripts building on the CDO package.

- `grib2netcdf.cdo`: this application converts the seasonal forecast data from the initial GRIB format to NetCDF and performs some simple additional computation which include the derivation of wind speed (wss) from the wind components ($u10$, $v10$) retrieved from the CDS, and the derivation of relative humidity (rh) using dew point temperature ($d2m$) and 2-meter atmospheric temperature ($t2m$). Also, this application derives daily cumulated values of rainfall and solar radiation which are normally available as total cumulated values from the beginning of the forecast until any future lead time.
- `hourly2daily.cdo`: this application works on the ERA5 reanalysis data, which are retrieved from the CDS as hourly records. The application computes the daily statistics and derives the values of wind speed (wss) and relative humidity (rh) using the same formulas adopted for the seasonal forecast data. The current version of the R package `CStools` requires that the observational data are split into different files for each month of the year. Therefore, the application `hourly2daily.cdo` performs also the splitting of data into monthly files.

Computation

After the pre-processing through `grib2netcdf.cdo` and `hourly2daily.cdo`, data are ready as an input for the bias correction and for the computation of bio-climatic indices. These two operations are performed by the following applications.

- `MEDGOLD_biascorrection.R`: This application prepares the bias-corrected data and makes them available for the end-users and as input for the computation of bio-climatic indices. The application uses as input the ensemble seasonal climate forecasts and the corresponding reference observational dataset. In principles, any gridded observational data can be adopted, provided that it has the same variables and the same of the output of the application `hourly2daily.cdo`, as it is illustrated in Figure 3-3. For the development of the MED-GOLD prototype, we have adopted ERA5 as the main reference observational data. A straightforward upgrade is the use of ERA5Land or AgERA5, also available on the Copernicus CDS, which have a higher spatial resolution and improved quality of some key parameters.

The application performs the following key operations.

1. Load the required data into the local workspace. Normally, the application uses the ensemble seasonal forecasts initialized at the latest available starting date, and the corresponding hindcasts initialized at the same starting date for all the available previous years. For example, the bias-correction of seasonal forecasts initialized on November 1st 2020, requires the corresponding hindcasts initialized on November 1st for all available previous years, typically from 1993, in order to determine a robust statistics for the modelled variables.

Similarly, the bias-correction application requires a reference observational dataset covering the same current and past years.

2. Sub-domain selection and interpolation. Using seasonal forecasts at high-spatial resolution may easily become very computationally demanding. Therefore, the application offers the possibility of sub-setting a

domain of interest. As a standard process in the CSTools data loading routines, observations and model data are all interpolated onto identical grids so they can be compared directly.

3. The core of the bias-correction algorithm is represented by the *CST_Calibration* and the *CST_QuantileMapping* algorithms included in the CSTools package. More details on the specific methodologies adopted for the bias-correction of the different variables are reported in Section 3.1.3
 4. Bias-corrected data are exported into output files, ready for the end-users. Two different formats, according to the needs of different types of users, are available:
 - a. NetCDF export files containing gridded data for the entire sub-domain selected in step 2. Each file contains a single variable for all time steps over the forecasting time-interval (6 months). This is the type of input which is required, for example, by DELPHI.
 - b. .csv export files containing time series for each single grid cell so that end-users can access only the required local data when requested, following the typical data needs of applications such as GRANODURO.NET®
- **MEDGOLD_clisagri.R:** This component derives several bioclimatic indicators which are relevant for the durum-wheat sector as discussed in the deliverable 4.7 (RD.2). It performs the following operations:
 1. Similarly to the bias correction application, Clisagri uses the ensemble seasonal forecasts initialized at the latest available starting date, and the corresponding hindcasts initialized at the same starting date for all available past years. Also, the evaluation of the skill scores requires the reference observational data for the current year and for all the past years available for the ensemble seasonal forecasts.
 2. Sub-domain selection and interpolation. This step is similar to the one develop for the bias-correction application.
 3. Integration of the observational data with the ensemble forecasts to allow the computation of bio-climatic indices. The bio-climatic indices for durum wheat are defined over a time interval covering 10 months, from September to June. While, seasonal forecasts are usually released with a maximum lead-time of around 6 months (except for the November run that has a 13-month lead time). Therefore, it is not possible to compute all the indicators using only data from the seasonal forecasts. Moreover, as the crop season is progressing, it is useful to profit from the available observational data in order to improve the quality of the end-of-season outlook. Similarly to the strategy adopted for DELPHI (see Figure 3-1), for each grid cell in the selected domain a working dataset is prepared by using all ensemble members of the seasonal forecast and following the following rules:
 - a. from September 1st to the starting date of the latest available forecast, the CLISAGRI working dataset is filled with the reference observational data, so that all member of the resulting ensemble share the same observed data during the initial time interval;
 - b. from the starting date until the last date of the forecast, the working dataset is filled with the members of the ensemble forecast;
 - c. from the end of the forecast until the end of the time interval over which the bio-climatic indices are defined (end of June), the working dataset is filled with observational data from a randomly selected year, so that the daily data show a plausible day-to-day variability while maintaining the expected climatic statistics.
 4. The computation of the bioclimatic indices is performed by sending properly formatted data to the CLISAGRI routines, described in more details in Section 3.2.3.
 5. Computation of the Ranked Probability Skill Score (RPSS) associated to the bio-climatic indicators so that the appropriate information on the reliability of the forecasts can be transferred to the users. Here, the RPSS is computed by comparing the bio-climatic indices based on the CLISAGRI integrated dataset described in step 2) with the same indicators calculated with the reference observational data (ERA5). The computation of RPSS is performed using the function `veriApply` include in the R package *EasyVerification*. In particular, the RPSS is computed by distinguishing three categories: below normal (lower tercile), normal (middle tercile) and above normal (upper tercile).
 6. The output files are prepared so that they can be used as an input to the seasonal forecast panel of the MED-GOLD visualization platform or for other external applications. The output files are structured in order to include a single record (e.g. gridded data for a single time step) for each file and include:
 - a. **values** of the bioclimatic indices for all members of the ensemble forecasts and for all the available years for the selected starting date;
 - b. **values** of the bioclimatic indices for both the reference observational data and all the available years for the selected starting date;

- c. **probability** associated to the considered terciles for all the available past years;
- d. **most likely tercile** according to the distribution of the ensemble forecasts and therefore to the probability associated to the considered terciles;
- e. **percentile** associated to the value of the bio-climatic index computed with the observational data;
- f. **RPSS** values as described at point 5) above.

The output is stored in NetCDF files and a new file is created for each year and for each starting date.

Output

The output of the computation layer is made available to external users through the API interface described in section 3.1.4. The output of the data processing pipeline includes:

- **NetCDF files** containing gridded bias-corrected seasonal forecast data over the selected subdomain;
- **.csv files** containing cell based bias corrected seasonal forecast data in zipped archives containing all variables that are normally required with crop models (i.e. daily values of mean temperature, maximum and minimum temperature, cumulated rainfall, wind speed, relative humidity and solar radiation);
- **NetCDF files** containing bioclimatic indices, their statistics and the associated skill scores and the corresponding values based on observational data.

3.1.3. BIAS CORRECTION

To reduce the biases associated to the predictions, MED-GOLD uses a simple bias adjustment approach in cross-validation to correct the raw predictions obtained from SEAS5 in order to drive the MED-GOLD models in the three selected Italian locations: Ravenna, Foggia and Jesi. More specifically, the raw and simple bias-adjusted daily seasonal predictions of precipitation, maximum and minimum temperatures from ECMWF SEAS5 prediction system have been used, considering mainly the starting dates of November and February. The observational dataset JRC-MarsMet and ERA5 have been used as a reference for both the bias adjustment and the forecast quality assessment [RD.2].

The procedure consists in:

1. Pick a test year. The training period is the whole period without the test year;
2. Calculate the monthly observed and forecasted (ensemble) average over the training period for both monthly temperature and precipitation: $\langle PRE_o \rangle$, $\langle PRE_f \rangle$, $\langle T_o \rangle$ and $\langle T_f \rangle$;
3. Bias adjusting all the individual forecast members over the test year:
 - a. $T^* = T_f - (\langle T_f \rangle - \langle T_o \rangle)$
 - b. $PRE^* = PRE_f \cdot (\langle PRE_o \rangle / \langle PRE_f \rangle)$
4. Repeat the steps 1-3 for all the available years.

The main resource adopted for the bias-correction of the input variables is the R package CSTools (<https://cran.r-project.org/web/packages/CSTools/index.html>).

Other variables (daily rainfall, relative humidity, wind speed and solar radiation) whose daily fluctuations are not expected to show a normal distribution around the mean are bias corrected using the quantile mapping methodology implemented in the *CST_QuantileMapping* function of the R package *CSTools*.

Several different configurations of the bias correction algorithm have been tested on these variables, in order to select the most appropriate and time efficient solution.

The different quantile mapping methods tested for the required input variables are:

- 'PTF' fitting a parametric transformations to the quantile-quantile relation of observed and modelled values.
- 'RQUANT' estimating the quantile-quantile relation of observed and modelled time series for regularly spaced quantiles using local linear least square regression.
- 'QUANT' estimating the empirical cumulative distribution function of observed and modelled time series for regularly spaced quantiles.
- 'SSPLIN' fitting a smoothing spline to the quantile-quantile plot of observed and modelled time series.

The comparison between the different methodologies is evaluated by considering the bias-correction applied mainly to minimum temperature, which illustrates well the main characteristics of the different methods. Main results for the site of Ravenna are shown in Figures 3-3 and 3-4.

The three methods PTF, QUANT and RQUANT provide an appropriate correction of the selected variable to the observed climatology. However, the methods QUANT and RQUANT create significant and unrealistic discontinuities in the data, in correspondence to the transition between adjacent sampling periods (Figures 3-3bcs 3-4bc), whereas the method PTF appears to be more appropriate for this type of application (Figures 3-3a, 3-4a). The method SSPLIN, which uses a spline to interpolate the quantile-quantile relation between observation and forecast, produces spurious values, far beyond the range of natural variability of the observed data. This behaviour of the SSPLIN method (Figures 3-3d, 3-4d) is observed for all variables examined in this analysis.

A comparison of the PTF method applied to all variables required for the downstream impact models in the durum wheat sector is presented in Figure 3-5. As shown in the Figure, the approximation adopted for the computation of relative humidity produced values above 100% that can be cured by correcting the bias with observation. In general, it is advisable to compute relative humidity from bias corrected temperature and dew point temperature data. On the other hand, downward solar radiation depends mainly on astronomical parameters and does not require further correction.

It is therefore possible to draw some general conclusion about the methodology to be adopted for the bias correction of daily data, required for the impact models developed within MED-GOLD (Section 3.2).

Temperature data (t2m, mn2t24, mx2t24) : (daily mean, minimum and maximum): use the CALIBRATION algorithm of CStools.

Daily cumulated rainfall: use the PTF method of quantile mapping, with sampling period of 30days.

Relative humidity (rh): compute rh from bias corrected temperature and dew point temperature, or apply PTF method of quantile mapping with sampling period of 30 days

Wind speed (wss): use the PTF method of quantile mapping, with sampling period of 30days.

Downward solar radiation (ssrd): no bias correction required.

Figure 3-3 Comparison of quantile mapping methods for the bias correction of temperature forecasts, using a sampling period of 43 days: PTF(a), QUANT(b), RQUANT(c), SSPLIN(d). Each dot represents a daily value from raw seasonal forecast ensemble members (red), the reanalysis ERA5 (black) and the bias corrected daily values (blue). For each day, data are extracted from a multi 10-year series covering the period 2010-2019.

Figure 3-4 As figure 3-3 but for a length of the sampling period of 30 days applied to the variable tp (total precipitation).

Figure 3-5 Examples of quantile mapping method PTF applied to all climate variables required for the MED-GOLD models. A sampling period of 30 days is adopted. Each dot represents a daily value from raw seasonal forecast ensemble members (red), the reanalysis ERA5 (black) and the bias corrected daily values (blue). For each day, data are extracted from a 27-year series covering the period 2010-2019.

3.1.4. INTERFACE WITH IMPACT MODELS

Figure 3-6 shows the complete workflow for running MED-GOLD impact models. Most of the steps involving the data collection and preparation by the MED-GOLD ICT platform have been described in Sections 3.1.2 and 3.1.3. This section focusses on the last step that is actually allowing the MED-GOLD model to access the required data.

Figure 3-6: The MED-GOLD ICT platform's services. The orange boxes represents the machine-to-machine workflow (from left to right) allowing either the on-line data visualizations (the last step on the right) or the data acquisition by the MED-GOLD models such as, for instance, the Granoduro.net DSS.

The workflow is instantiated by Granoduro.net® (for instance) upon calling a specific REST API endpoint on MED-GOLD's ICT platform's infrastructure – after receiving an authentication token by calling ICT platform's authentication API – and passing along all the needed parameters that identify the specific geographical point, the data variables to fetch, and a temporal range.

The ICT Platform then validates Granoduro.net®'s request and internally checks for the availability of data files needed to fulfil the requests. In case they are already available, the ICT platform's storage subsystem prepares a ZIP archive containing all the needed files and sends back its downloading link to Granoduro.net®. If one or more of the needed files are not already cached in the storage subsystem, a state machine gets instantiated to take care of the files generation. A simplified diagram of the internal state machine, implemented using AWS's Lambda Step Function is shown in Figure 3-7.

The API call is always answered synchronously with a message containing either a downloading link or the information that the requested data files are being prepared. A request id is always passed along within the answer message and can be passed as a parameter to another REST API endpoint to gather information about the pending request status in order to allow the user to keep track of the pending request.

All the relevant API calls implementing this workflow are documented in detail in ANNEX A.

Figure 3-7: Simplified diagram of the MED-GOLD impact models workflow in the ICT Platform

3.2. THE MED-GOLD DURUM WHEAT MODELS

3.2.1. DELPHI

The Delphi is a FORTRAN-based mechanistic crop model calibrated and maintained by the CNR. Delphi is used operationally by the CNR in order to provide the forecast of durum wheat yield and quality in Italy to Barilla. Delphi ability to simulate crop growth, yield and product quality was validated well before MED-GOLD [RD.7, RD.8, RD.9]. The current status of Delphi as well as its evolution within MED-GOLD is reported in previous reports [e.g. RD.2] and summarized here. A special attention is devoted to the explanation of the driving data configuration strategy to merge observational and model data, which is shared by the other MED-GOLD models as well (Section 3.2.2. and 3.2.3).

In brief, Delphi accounts for water and nitrogen cycles in the soil and in the plant. Input weather data at daily time scale are the air temperature (maximum, minimum and average), global shortwave radiation, total precipitation, wind speed (average) and relative humidity (average). Input data for the main physiological parameters of the durum wheat cultivars, sowing date and number of seeds/m², the soil hydrological profile, soil total nitrogen content profile, agronomic data on quality and quantity of nitrogen and roots growth data are also required [RD.10].

The Delphi system starts simulating plant growth the 1st of September and it continues at the daily time step till the harvest date. In the operational version, the model runs simulations from January to June. The crop dynamics is determined by the observed weather conditions during the period from 1st September to the current date when the system is run, while the following development till harvest is determined by the conditions provided by scenarios data. The configuration of the different input data in the standard Delphi implementation is depicted in Figure 3-8.

The standard Delphi system uses three scenario ("dry", "wet", "average") derived from the observed long-term conditions (1981– 2010) and defined as the wettest, driest and average crop years. This strategy provides a sort of ensemble forecast allowing to determine an outlook of the final yield at any stage of the growing season, with an associated uncertainty range. As soon as the availability of observed data increases during the growing season, the predictions become more accurate (but its usefulness decreases).

In MED-GOLD, Delphi has been modified in order to be driven by seasonal forecast data provided by Copernicus Climate Data Store released in October 2017 and consisting of 51-members simulations lasting for 6 months (see RD.2). These

data, accesses through the MED-GOLD ICT platform, replace the ‘Scenario Data’ in the months of time depicted in yellow and violet in Figure 3-8. Since the last month of data necessary to reach the harvesting date is not covered by the seasonal forecast released in October, it is replaced with the data of the average scenario based on observed long-term conditions.

Figure 3-8: Configuration of the forcing data for the DELPHI simulation during the different phases of the growing season. Observation and simulated data used for the forcing are merged in different proportions ensuring the best consistency with reality and an increasing accuracy of the forecast as long as the end of the growing season is approached.

The new configurations is already extensively tested and used to assess the effects of the bias correction [RD.2]. For the three MED-GOLD Italian case studies (Jesi, Ravenna, Foggia) simulation are conducted, starting from October 1st, and analysed at a monthly time step. Results have been compared with the ones of the standard Delphi System driven by with the three reference weather scenarios based on historical observations (dry, average, wet scenario). The results with all the ensembles and the dry-average-wet scenarios and charts with average, percentiles 25th-75th for all ensembles predictions, were provided to Barilla. Its feedback is summarized in D4.7 [RD.2]. Daily outputs have been analysed as well for a selection of simulations.

Figure 3-9: As figure 3-8, but for the ‘bad year’ and ‘good years’ MED-GOLD narrative.

Hindcast simulations for ‘bad’ and ‘good’ years are conducted as well, following the MED-GOLD narrative, for two starting dates (Figure 3-9). The identified ‘bad years’ (below average yield) are 2010 for Ravenna and 2007 for both Foggia and Ancona. ‘Good year’ (above average yield) are 2012 for Ravenna and 2016 for both Foggia and Ancona. In this case,

model simulations are based on the seasonal predictions of the hindcast released in February and in April for each crop year (25 ensemble for 6 months of forecast). Results have been compared with the those of the traditional Delphi System.

Furthermore hindcast simulations are conducted for 31 years (1988 - 2018) and based both on biased and unbiased ensemble hindcast released in February (25 members). For each simulation the input weather files were built as indicated in Figure 3-10:

Figure 3-10: As figure 3-8, but for 31 years (1988-2018) and based on ERA5 reanalysis data and scenario data.

Results were compared with the results of the Delphi System by feeding the model with ERA5 reanalysis dataset for each crop year (from 1st September to harvest date) and with the results of the current Delphi System by feeding the model with ERA5 reanalysis dataset (from 1st September till 31st January) + synthetic weather scenarios based on historical observations (dry, average, wet scenario). These results were evaluated by BARILLA that is providing the main user feedback for the DELPHI development, which is generally positive and largely optimistic (see [RD.2]).

3.2.2. GRANODURO.NET®

Granoduro.net® is an interactive web-based Decision Support System (DSS) for high-quality sustainable wheat farming [see RD.16, RD.17 and RD.18]. Granoduro.net® collects crop data in real time through sensors and scouting tools, it organizes the data in a cloud system, it interpret them via advanced modelling and big data techniques, and it integrate them automatically, generating information, alarms and decision support advice. The employed databases also include farming data in order to provide a comprehensive and continuous flow of updated crop related information.

In general DSSs do not replace agricultural practitioners or entrepreneurs. However Granoduro.net® have proven its added value in providing additional information to support crop farming decision-making processes. Indeed, the user feedback for Granoduro.net® and the expert meeting identifying the relevant climate information to be included in the MED-GOLD development [RD.1, RD.2] have been collected on a selection of the wide population of enthusiastic Granoduro.net® users, composed by experts and farmers contributing to the BARILLA production line.

Among other models and functionalities, Granoduro.NET® contains a durum wheat phenological model based on the work of Rossi et al. [RD.19], which requires daily temperature data as input variable. This model is already calibrated for several durum wheat varieties. It simulates the crop growth, passing through the main phases: emergence, tillering, stem elongation, booting, heading, flowering, and maturity.

Predicting when the main phenological stages will be reached allows to identify the relevant periods for decision making in advance, which is of primary importance for the calculation of climatic indexes identified during the Project [RD.1, RD.2]. Therefore, this component of Granoduro.net® has been selected to be improved using bias-corrected seasonal forecast driving data taking advantage of the ICT platform developed within MED-GOLD. This effort resulted in a completely new functionality of Granoduro.net®.

Figure 3-11 provides a graphical representation of the GRANODURO.NET® functionalities for different fields. The icon at the end allows accessing the new ones developed with MED-GOLD.

These have been described in some detail in the previous reports [RD.1, RD.2], which discuss the preliminary results obtained for the three MED-GOLD target locations. For these locations (Ravenna, Jesi and Foggia), the phenological model is run from sowing date using observed weather data till they are available, and then is fed with seasonal forecasts data till maturity is reached in a similar configuration as that described for the DELPHI system (Section 3.2.1). For these tests, a selection of three wheat varieties with different development cycle (short, average, long), are considered. This effort, conducted for the hindcasts, actually mimics an operational framework in which the forecasts can updated as soon as new releases of bias corrected seasonal forecasts become available in the ICT platform, i.e. on a monthly base.

The results of the phenological model driven by seasonal forecast data together with the dynamical computations of the climatic indexes developed within MED-GOLD (see section 3.2.3) are discussed in the second user feedbacks report [RD.2].

Figure 3-11: Example view of the GRANODURO.NET® DSS for different plots. The different icons represent the different information provided, with the new MED-GOLD capability highlighted in yellow.

Gestione	ID	O.P.	Utente	Azienda	Descrizione	Nazione	Località	Varietà	Superficie (ha)	Coltivazione	Funzionalità
	141947	La Marca Grains-Supervisor. La Marca-G.A.I.A.	G.a.i.a. Soc. Agr. Coop.	G.a.i.a. Soc. Agr. Coop. (G.a.i.a. Soc. Agr. Coop.)	Castelli Offida GRD 20	Italia	Offida	Farsh	6,97	Convenzionale (difesa integrata obbligatoria)	
	141944	La Marca Grains-Supervisor. La Marca-G.A.I.A.	G.a.i.a. Soc. Agr. Coop.	G.a.i.a. Soc. Agr. Coop. (G.a.i.a. Soc. Agr. Coop.)	Calvaresi-Acciam GRR 20	Italia	Ripatransone	Secolo	8,53	Convenzionale (difesa integrata obbligatoria)	
	141941	La Marca Grains-Supervisor. La Marca-G.A.I.A.	G.a.i.a. Soc. Agr. Coop.	G.a.i.a. Soc. Agr. Coop. (G.a.i.a. Soc. Agr. Coop.)	Marchetti Campoflone GRR 20	Italia	Campoflone	Secolo	11,21	Convenzionale (difesa integrata obbligatoria)	
	141921	CON.CER.	Lombardi Antonio 56	Lombardi Antonio 56 (Lombardi Antonio 56)	Aureo foglio 3	Italia	Bovino	Aureo	9,93	Convenzionale (difesa integrata obbligatoria)	

In addition to climate related risks, Granoduro.net® is going to provide users with anticipated information on the risk posed during the growing season by the main wheat diseases (Figure 3-12) using newly developed indexes exclusively based on weather data (temperature and rain). These new indexes, adapted from previous instances, have been defined specifically for MED-GOLD in order to be computable from seasonal forecast daily data.

The main wheat disease considered in MED-GOLD for durum wheat are stripe rust (caused by *Puccinia striiformis*), leaf rust (caused by *Puccinia triticina*), stem rust (caused by *Puccinia graminis* subs. *graminis*), powdery mildew (caused by *Erisiphe graminis* f.sp. *tritici*), Septoria blotch (caused by *Mycosphaerella graminicola* and *Leptosphaeria nodorum*) and Fusarium Head blight (caused by fungi of the genus *Fusarium*, mainly *F. graminearum* and *F. culmorum*).

Figure 3-12. Example implementation of the Granoduro.net® phenological model allowing to diagnose climate related risk in advance, using seasonal forecast data. The different colors represent the different levels of disease risk, in this case, for the different phenological stages. Similar automatic plots allow estimating the climatic risks related to drought, rain, frost and heat stresses.

For each disease, wheat growth stages during which disease development is possible and pose a threat for the crop have been computed with the phenological model using again the seasonal forecast information provided by the MED-GOLD ICT platform. For each causal agent, temperature conditions allowing fungal development have been retrieved from literature. This information is used to identify days having suitable conditions for fungal development in the relevant periods, or to calculate the number of disease cycle that can be completed in the relevant period. Risk classes have been identified on the base of the percentage of days having suitable conditions for disease development in the period, going from red (high risk) to orange, yellow and green (low risk). Example results from this additional Granoduro.net® component has been provided, again, in the second user feedback report [RD.2].

3.2.3. CLISAGRI

CLISAGRI is a dedicated R package for agro-climate services developed by the JRC (previously named “RagroClim” in D4.7) specifically for MED-GOLD, designed through the interactions with durum wheat climate information end-users. This innovative climate service tool has been a direct result of the needs and knowledge collected from the interactions with end-users and experts in the field. A paper, describing its use as a part of a tailored climate service, is currently under review in *Climate Services* [RD.5].

Although CLISAGRI has been developed to serve WP4, it is conceived in such a way that its application can be easily extended to other crops, time scales, and spatial scale (even reaching the global one). Thus, it is going to be expanded also to cover the olive and grape sectors, the global scale for durum wheat, and mid- end-of-the-century climate projections.

More specifically, CLISAGRI integrates a dynamic crop phenology model with an approach based on dedicated agro-climate indicators assessing the risks associated with unfavourable/extreme weather and climate conditions during

sensitive crop growth stages. Concerning its first implementation for durum wheat, the initial set of the agro-climate indicators has been developed in a co-design approach with a consortium of durum wheat farmers during the first users' feedback workshop and they are listed and discussed in detail in the second user feedback report [RD.2]. Four groups of indicators have been identified characterizing drought events, excessive wetness, cold and heat stress (Figure 3-13).

As in Granoduro.net (Section 3.2.2), an important component of Clisagri is the dynamic phenological model used to account for the climatic effects on the timing of the development stages of durum wheat, which is needed to define the sensitive periods consistently with the climate and weather anomalies characterizing the season under analysis (which can accelerate or slow down the development stages of the crop). In order to facilitate the dissemination and the application of Clisagri, both the dynamic phenology model and the computation of the agro-climatic indicators have been implemented as a new R package.

Figure 3-13 Schematic representation of the four groups of indicators that are identified by the end-users in order to characterize hydrological balance, excessive wetness, cold stress and heat stress conditions through the phenological phases of durum wheat.

The Clisagri phenological component includes two options corresponding to different levels of complexity and different numbers of parameters that need to be calibrated, a simpler one with two growing degree day sum parameters and a more complex one involving six growing degree day sum parameters. At this stage of the project, CLISAGRI has been successfully implemented in seasonal forecasts (see RD.2) for generic durum wheat varieties ('fast', 'slow', 'average'). Clisagri includes a calibration procedure that needs observational data of phenological phase succession for different durum wheat variety. Moreover, the calibration parameters can be tuned in order to mimic the effects of genotyping and breeding, especially for application to the decadal and climate change time—scales.

The package also provides a set of optimization functions, which target optimal variety selection in terms of crop cycle duration to avoid unfavourable/extreme weather and climate events during the sensitive growth stages that are useful for breeders.

Figure 3-14 shows a breeding exercise conducted for the recent past by considering two important MED-GOLD indicators for drought and heat stress. Different combinations of the phenological parameters related to Tsum1 and Tsum2 define new durum wheat varieties that can potentially be obtained by breeding. This powerful tool provides a simple way to derive clear result as, in this case, the combination of genes to limit heat stress between flowering and maturity, which is detrimental for the final yield [RD.4; RD.5; RD.6]. The figure also shows an example of how to use the software, to allow the replicability of this result.

Figure 3-14: Simulated hydrological balance between heading and maturity (panel a) and number of hot days between flowering and maturity, based on durum wheat varieties characterized by different combinations of Tsum1/Tsum2 (indicated by different colors). To distinguish between different combinations, the color of each simulated indicator is related to scale in panel c, with each color representing a unique combination of Tsum1/Tsum2. The R code to produce the indicator of type 16 (number of hot days) is shown in panel b.

3.2.4. WOFOST-ECROPS

The other modelling component of the prototype is based on an innovative crop growth model designed for massive simulations, named ECroPS. ECroPS is written in python and it is optimized to run in MPI-environments. The code is planned to be released under the EUPL licence in the coming months.

The core of the model is based on WOFOST [RD.6], but it has some new key parametrization schemes that have been developed during MED-GOLD, which are the response to elevated CO₂ concentration and the effect of heat stress at flowering, which is poorly accounted or even neglected by most crop models. The first one simulates the main effects on allocated biomass and transpiration of elevated CO₂ concentration, differentiated for C₃ (e.g. wheat) and C₄ (e.g. maize) crops, and it is based on the available experimental evidence collected in FACE/non-FACE experiments. It is designed to run probabilistically to take into account the uncertainties and the different responses observed in the experimental studies. However, it does not (yet) reproduce the stabilisation effect observed at around 600 ppm. The second one has been designed to reproduce the impacts of heat stress at flowering that can heavily reduce final yield. This component is still under testing by using FACE experimental studies as reference. An improved soil-water modelling component is currently under testing as well as the one simulating nitrogen fertilisation.

The specific wheat parametrizations (as well as the soil parameters) cover at the moment the European domain and are derived from the ones used by JRC in the operational MARS crop monitoring and forecasting system (MCYFS). While it is the only MED-GOLD model that is not implemented on seasonal forecast data yet, it is the only one providing preliminary results for the future climate scenarios (see Section 4.2.2)

4. APPLICATION TO CLIMATE CHANGE

Agronomic decision such as field operations, crop breeding, investment in infrastructures an in new cropping areas and policy planning for adaptation strategies require climate anticipation over longer time-scales than those covered by the seasonal forecasts [RD.1]. Climate predictions at the decadal and multi-decadal time scales can provide useful information to address these questions.

This chapter shows some preliminary results focused on the decadal and multi-decadal time scales and anticipates the envisaged application of the MED-GOLD modelling approaches at such scales. Section 4.1 describes the differences between the new decadal climate predictions and the traditional climate scenarios projections. It presents the results on the application of decadal predictions of a drought indicator similar to some of the ones defined in MED-GOLD. It also describes the required data processing for climate projections, which are still the reference products to address the multi-decadal time-scales (section 4.1.2). Section 4.2 discusses how the MED-GOLD models can be applied at the time-scales of climate change, showing some preliminary results of yield projections in Europe and possible adaptation options. Section 4.3 anticipates the additional innovative product that will be delivered by MEDGOLD, i.e. the assessment of the future suitability of durum wheat at the global scale.

4.1. DECADAL VARIABILITY VS. CLIMATE CHANGE

Since the MED-GOLD project has already been effective in delivering the poorly understood concept of probabilistic climate information to end-users at the seasonal time-scale [RD.1], this section aims at shedding light on another critical and controversial concept related to the very chaotic – but partially predictable – nature of the climate system.

The evolution of the climate system at the decadal time-scale depends on the changes in atmospheric composition and other external forcings as well as in the internally component of climate variability [RD.11]. Until very recently, the only sources of future climate information that were available for decision support systems and impact assessments were seasonal predictions and climate projections. These are conceptually different problems (see Figure 4-1).

Figure 4-1. Schematic illustration of the progression from initial value problems, with daily weather forecasts at one end, and multidecadal to century projections as a forced boundary problem at the other, with seasonal and decadal prediction in between (source [RD.11]).

At the seasonal timescale, for a period ranging from 1 to 18 months into the future, the climate evolution mainly depends on the initial condition and the internally generated variability of the climate system (i.e. that related to the so-called 'butterfly effect') and less on the changes in the externally forced components that occur over the period of forecast (i.e. greenhouse gases, solar cycle, landuse changes, large volcanoes, etc.).

On the other hand, climate projections providing a future outlook of the earth's climate system covering a continuous temporal range from the past century to the end of this century (or beyond) are solely driven by changes in external forcings. In these simulations, several features related to internal variability are often regarded as simple noise and filtered out in the multi-model ensemble averages.

In order to address the stakeholders needs, traditional climate scenarios have been used to generate climate information for the next decades neglecting somehow the memory of the initial condition and the effects of internal variability. This is equivalent to picking any of the possible random trajectories of the climate system rather than the closer to the observed one, but there was no better alternative until recently.

A growing body of literature have pointed out the importance of the internally generated climate variability operating at decadal timescale, which is responsible for rapid climate variations over large parts of the globe including Europe and the Mediterranean area [RD.12, RD.13, RD.14]. Indeed, the recent summer warming of Southern Europe is actually due to a superposition of the shift towards the warm phase of the Northern Atlantic seas surface temperature (i.e. the Atlantic Multidecadal Oscillation, or Atlantic Multidecadal Variability) on top of the slower effect of global warming.

The recently developed decadal climate prediction systems attempt to fill the gap existing between seasonal predictions and climate change projections, addressing the time scale ranging from one year ahead up to a decade (see Figure 4-1). Decadal predictions are, in simple terms, an extension of the seasonal ones wherein climate models are initialized by introducing observation-based data and run for a decade or so under the influence of contemporaneous changing external forcings, similarly to climate change projections.

Figure 4-2 presents an example of decadal predictions over Europe (in orange) compared to the range of traditional uninitialized climate model simulations (in grey) and to the observation (in black). The ensemble mean of climate model simulations is consistent with the observed long-term trend. However, the inter-annual variability is underestimated, because the internal variability components (as reproduced by the model) are not always in phase and the fluctuations tend to cancel each other when considering the model ensemble mean. In particular, the ensemble mean of the historical climate simulations fails at reproducing the cooling observed in Europe from the 1960s to the 1980s (see RD.12, RD.13).

Figure 4-2. Example of initialized decadal predictions for annual 2-meter temperature anomaly over Europe (orange lines) in comparison to the standard uninitialized climate model historical simulation (in grey) and the future climate change scenario simulation (in violet). The corresponding observational data is plotted in black.

The initialized decadal climate predictions, aiming at capturing the observed inter-annual variability, are shown in Figure 4-2 (in orange). While the ensemble of the uninitialized climate model simulations produces a smooth tendency towards a warmer climate, decadal predictions variability can produce more realistic results, more consistent with the observations. These predictions are actually able to capture the rapid warming observed after 1996, the stationary climate of the early 1980s, and the cooling observed in the late 1960s. At the time these decadal predictions were produced, they correctly predicted the 'hiatus' around 2010.

Therefore, decadal climate predictions could better capture the actual trajectory of the climate system in the near future and could potentially predict the occurrence of the climate anomalies superimposed to the global warming signal. Decadal predictions may provide an important gain in terms of predicting unfavourable climate conditions that may heavily affects the agricultural sector. Since the decadal time-scale has been identified as paramount for durum wheat activities such as breeding and other kinds of investments [RD.1], this innovative approach is introduced in MED-GOLD as well. Preliminary results are shown in the Section 4.1.1.

4.1.1. DECADAL PREDICTIONS OF DROUGHT

This section illustrates the potential usefulness of decadal predictions for building a climate service for agronomical and economical needs through assessing the forecast quality of multi-model climate predictions in estimating two user-relevant drought indices, SPEI (Standardized Precipitation Evapotranspiration Index) and SPI (Standardized Precipitation Index, see [RD.2]), at multi-annual timescales during European summer.

This analysis, which is described in detail in a peer-review paper [RD.15], is conducted using a comprehensive set of decadal hindcasts (i.e. forecast simulations conducted for the past climate) from six different decadal forecast systems that were produced as part of the Coupled Model Intercomparison Project Phase 5 (CMIP5) and the European Union's Seventh Framework Programme for Research (FP7) - SPECS project, to build a large multi-model ensemble forecast. The model ensemble includes the following general circulation models: CanCM4, EC-Earth v2, GFDLCM2p1, HadCM3, MIROC5, and MPI-ESM-LR (see RD.15 for details on these models). Each model produced two different sets of experiments. The first set corresponds to 10-year initialized hindcasts that were run by explicitly prescribing the actual state of the climate system at the start of the simulation (in the month of November every year from 1960 to 2005). The second set is the corresponding ensemble that is not initialized and is used as a reference to investigate the impact of initialization.

Figure 4-3. Maximum positive correlation values among the considered drought indices with initialized decadal prediction (first column) during the summer months (July, August and September) over the European region. Green and blue colour indicate the maximum correlation obtained with the SPEI6 and SPI6 respectively. The second column presents the (positive) correlation difference between the best performing drought index in the initialized forecasts and the best performing drought index in the uninitialized forecasts (left and right column, respectively) Negative correlations appear in white.

Results point to high skill for predicting 5-year average (forecast years 1-5) SPEI across Southern Europe, while for the same forecast period SPI exhibits high and significant skill over Scandinavia and its surrounding regions (top row of Figure 4-3). These results demonstrate the added value of initialized decadal climate information with respect to standard uninitialized climate projections. The model initialization improves the forecast skill especially over Central Europe, the Balkan region and Southern Scandinavia (bottom row of Figure 4-3).

Future extension of this work will focus on the development of a probabilistic forecast assessment of the drought indices for the timing on the year of interest for durum wheat, as identified in MED-GOLD.

4.1.2. BIAS CORRECTED CLIMATE SCENARIOS

Standard climate projections from 11 high-resolution EURO-CORDEX regional model simulations, covering Europe and the Mediterranean, have been provided by the JRC to start exploring climate change impacts on durum wheat and the effects of adaptation strategies. Mid-range (RCP4.5) and high-end (RCP8.5) emission scenarios are considered. Bias adjustment had been applied to daily precipitation, minimum and maximum temperatures. As for the seasonal forecasts (Section 3.1.3), bias adjustment was not performed for wind speed simulations.

This regional dataset has the advantage of being already bias corrected, allowing the implementation of threshold-dependent impact models such as the MED-GOLD ones. The results presented here can be extended at the global scale, as soon as bias corrected global climate model simulation from CMIP6 will be available as well.

Figure 4-4. Probability density of the number of hot days during the grain filling period (left) and of the hydrological balance during entire growing period of durum wheat in Ravenna (right) for the reference period (1981-2010) and mid of 21st Century (2041-2070). No adaptation measures were assumed in the computations (source [RD.5]).

Figure 4-4 shows an example of climate change diagnostic for Ravenna, one of the MED-GOLD target locations, for two Clisagri indicators. The left panel represents the occurrence frequency of heat stress at flowering, an extremely damaging climate effect for wheat [RD.3]. This harmful event is going to occur more frequently and with larger amplitude in the future climate, according to the RCP8.5 scenario [RD.5]. In addition, dry years are occurring more frequently as well, as indicated by the larger frequency of negative SPEI (Figure 4-4, right panel).

This result already provides useful information for the target location that can be translate into practical recommendations such as the need of field management to hold more water than the current soil does and the need of identifying and developing faster and less water demanding varieties, for instance.

4.2. THE MED-GOLD MODELS APPLICATION TO THE FURTHER FUTURE

All the modelling approaches developed in MED-GOLD can in principle be run at the climatic scales and at the global level because the nature and the format of the climate model outputs is essentially the same of the seasonal forecasts. However, serious limitations exist on the determination of the needed parameters and variables related to the specific field, the durum wheat variety, the employed infrastructure and other important user related decisions such as the planting date, fertilization amount and timing and plant protection [RD.21]. The data demand issue can affect the different models at a different level, depending on the number of involved parameters. The effects of the future adaptation options represent another important unknown for which realistic scenarios need to be set up (in fact, this might very well be one of the main MED-GOLD contributions).

Wofost.ECROPS, which is not implemented on the seasonal forecast yet, has the merits on having already been calibrated, implemented and run on large spatial scales, covering the entire Europe [RD.7].

The climate projections of durum wheat yield in mid-century with Wofost.ECROPS (Section 3.2.4) driven by CORDEX data (Section 4.1.2), and the testing of adaptation strategies focused on optimal sowing and cultivar are shown in Figures 4-5 and 4-6, respectively.

Yield forecast for 85p water limited - Durum wheat
Relative differences - aggregated values at NUTS 2 level
- 2050

Figure 4-5 Projected ensemble median of durum wheat yield changes (% w.r.t. the historical period) under the RCP8.5 scenario. Hatching denotes area having low models' agreement.

The first preliminary results obtained by using the bias-adjusted regional climate model simulations with WOFOST-ECroPS assume no changes in the agro-management as well as simplified adaptation strategies, e.g. sowing of cultivars reaching earlier flowering but having grain filling length similar to the current ones. Figure 4-5 shows the estimated changes (in % with respect to the historical simulations) for mid-century under the RCP8.5 scenario. A clear north-south dipole is visible, with losses affecting almost all southern European regions, despite the beneficial effect of elevated CO₂ concentration.

Optimal adaptation strategies may be able to offset these losses and in some cases even turn into gains. Preliminary simulations performed with ideotypes reaching earlier maturity show very promising results although affected by higher uncertainty (Fig. 4-6). However, it is important to underline that these preliminary runs did not include the new heat stress parametrization schemes (see Section 3.2.4), thus, underestimate the impacts of extremes [RD.3]. Furthermore, even in case of yield gain, elevated CO₂ concentration will pose a threat to quality in terms of protein and minerals concentration.

Yield forecast for 85p water limited - Durum wheat
Relative differences - aggregated values at NUTS 2 level
using Adaptation Strategy variety 1 - 2050

Figure 4-6 Projected ensemble median of durum wheat yield changes (% w.r.t. the historical period) under the RCP8.5 scenario assuming new cultivars (ideotypes reaching earlier flowering but having a similar grain filling length when compared to the current ones) are sown . Hatching denotes area having low models' agreement.

4.3. IDENTIFICATION OF NEW SUITABLE AREAS FOR DURUM WHEAT

Knowledge of potential distributions and habitat preferences of durum wheat under current and future climate conditions are vital for policy makers and stakeholders to develop suitable adaptation measures to mitigate against any detrimental effects of climate change. In this respect, MED-GOLD is developing a strategy to evaluate the range of compatible climatic conditions for durum wheat at the global scale in order to identify suitable growing areas in the present climate and future climate scenarios.

A main difficulty in tracking and analysing global durum wheat production is the lack of data. In fact, durum wheat production is merged with soft wheat in the official agricultural production statistics provided by FAOSTAT and in the main state-of-the-art global crop distribution datasets such as MIRCA2000. In contrast, MED-GOLD can take advantage on an expert driven dataset of average global durum wheat production collected and provided by BARILLA (see Figure 4.7). Furthermore, BARILLA developed and shared spatially explicit information of the areas growing durum wheat, which is represented in Figure 4-8.

Durum Wheat Main Basins

Figure 4-7. Annual mean durum wheat production (in million TONS) for the main growing areas in the World (source BARILLA).

Major Durum Wheat Production Areas

Figure 4-8. Delineations of the main durum wheat production areas at the global scale (source BARILLA).

MED-GOLD is further processing the information presented in Figure 4-8 by intersecting the durum wheat areas delineated by BARILLA with MIRCA2000, which provides also the spatial density of wheat plantations for different cropping strategies (winter/spring irrigated/rainfed wheat) together with reference planting and harvesting timing. Figure

4-9 shows the main results of such integration, which can be used to develop an objective climate suitability analysis for durum wheat. For each class, the same dataset provide information on the reference planting and harvesting months.

Figure 4-9. Spatial distribution of winter durum wheat estimated by MED-GOLD. The colours represent the share of grid area with the presence of durum wheat. The regular grid has a resolution of 5 arc min, which translates to roughly 9.2 km at the equator.

The spatial distribution of the main durum wheat growing regions shown in Figure 4-9, together with the basic temporal information related to the growing season, can be used as an input data to the suitability analysis aiming at identifying the current optimal (or more frequent) climate and the range of compatible climates for durum wheat cultivation.

The suitability analysis will be conducted with an algorithm based on support vector networks, which are supervised learning models with associated learning algorithms that incorporate data for multi-level classification.

The observed climate variables needed to build the suitability model are based on literature review (e.g. [RD.21, RD.22]) and, again, expert judgement:

- global solar radiation between sowing and anthesis,
- global solar radiation between anthesis and maturity,
- rainfall between sowing and anthesis,
- rainfall between anthesis and maturity,
- reference evapotranspiration between anthesis and maturity,
- minimum temperature between anthesis and maturity, and
- maximum temperature between anthesis and maturity.

The above climatic variables are often identified as the main driving factors for different agronomic traits of durum wheat, such as cumulative dry weight, number of tillers and grain filling rate [RD.20], which determine the final yield [RD.21].

Once the model is developed, the impact of climate change on suitability for durum wheat growth can be estimated using the bias-corrected future climate projections discussed in section 4.1.2. or bias corrected global climate models, when available.

5. CONCLUSION

This documents reports the current state of the MED-GOLD project in a critical period when the main ideas and concept have already taken a definite shape and several activities reached a stage that is close to the final form. The MED-GOLD prototype, co-design with farmers and professionals of the durum wheat production and processing chain, is essentially ready to be used operationally in a seasonal forecast context (see Chapter 3). With reference to Figure 3-1 and 3-6, the components of MED-GOLD already applicable to seasonal forecasts are the ICT platform downloading data from Copernicus CDS, the Delphi crop model, the Granoduro.net DSS and the Clisagri risk assessment software.

Notably, MED-GOLD has been effective in training the users to interpret the probabilistic information delivered by the seasonal forecast models' chain during the first confrontation with end-users [RD.1]. At the second users' feedback interaction step, the level of MED-GOLD development of the envisaged climate service prototype has been evaluated essentially positively [RD.2], despite the fact that the peak of the covid-19 pandemic in Italy and the consequent lockdown have delayed several of the project activities.

Complementary activities have been launched to showcase how MedGOLD prototype can provide support to deal with the longer time scales in order to answer different questions and support different decisions such as indications for breeders, investors and guidelines on adaptation options for farmers and policy makers. These activities, currently investigated with the crop model Wofost.ECroPS and with additional suitability analyses, are thought to provide more general information at larger spatial scale as well.

In this respect, a dedicated section of this document (Section 4.1) aim at shedding light onto another source of misunderstanding for users when addressing climate changes, which is the difference between the internal (natural) climate variability and the externally driven climate change i.e. the so called 'global warming'. The first one is associated to oscillation and climate variation that in principle could happen without the human influence on the climate system. The second is the component that is mainly driven by increase greenhouse gases.

Internal climate variability can produce relatively rapid climate variations at the decadal time scale (that are often confused with climate change), more relevant for farmers and stakeholders. The effects of global warming, more relevant for policy makers, will prevail over longer time-scales. MED-GOLD raises awareness on this controversial topic highlighting the correct methodology to produce climate information at the decadal and multidecadal time scales. While the latter can be addresses with the traditional scenario simulation conducted with the standard global circulation models, the climate of the next year can be better predicted with the recently developed decadal climate prediction systems.

In conclusion, the development of the MED-GOLD durum wheat prototype is on track. It provides a unique combination of tools and approaches to deal with the complexity of the agricultural sector. Almost all of them are ready, and first testing exercises have been successfully performed and evaluated by end-users. Indeed, the prototype has been already proven effective in supporting a broad range of users acting at different levels and scales. However, much more has been promised, especially for the application to the further future (decadal and multi-decadal time-scales). The final version climate service prototype will be completed during the next and last phase of MED-GOLD while still collecting and taking into account the users' feedback.

ANNEX A. CONNECTOR API DOCUMENTATION

A.1 GET /dataset/ecmwf/workflow/horta

GRANODURO.NET® workflow

The endpoint returns a link to an archive of datafiles generated according to passed parameters

REQUEST

QUERY PARAMETERS

NAME	TYPE	DESCRIPTION
*lat	string	latitude value of required point
*lon	string	longitude value of required point
*vars	enum ALLOWED: tmin2m, tma 2m, totprec, ssrd, 2d, 10u, 10v	list of variables required
*months	array of string	list of months required
*years	array of string	list of years required

RESPONSE

STATUS CODE - 200: link of zip file which contains a file csv for each ensemble in ecmwf files for selected point

RESPONSE MODEL - application/json: if elaboration is possible and required for the first time

```
{
  id: string id of elaboration
  message: string Data not available.,We are working to elaborate it
}
```

RESPONSE MODEL - application/json: if file already exists

```
{
  data: string id of elaboration
}
```



```
state: string state of elaboration
```

```
}
```

STATUS CODE - 401: Unhauthorized

RESPONSE MODEL - application/json

```
{
```

```
  message string unauthorize error message
```

```
}
```

STATUS CODE - 404: Not found

RESPONSE MODEL - application/json

```
{
```

```
  message string not found error message
```

```
}
```

A.2 GET /request/horta/

GRANODURO.NET® workflow

Horta workflow elaboration

This endpoint returns information of a given pending request, whose id has been returned by A.1 endpoint.

REQUEST

QUERY PARAMETERS

NAME	TYPE	DESCRIPTION
*id	string	id of request return by api workflow elaboration

RESPONSE

STATUS CODE - 200: returns id of elaboration or link of required file

RESPONSE MODEL - application/json: if elaboration is not terminated

```
{  
  state: string state of elaboration  
}
```

RESPONSE MODEL - application/json : : if elaboration is terminated

```
{  
  Data: string link of .zip file  
  state: string state of elaboration  
}
```

